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Investigating the influence of organizational culture on team management: exploring effective factors and techniques

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Abstract

This qualitative research examines how organizational culture intersects with team management in the construction industry. Conducting interviews with nine experienced construction project managers and team members, we collected data using a qualitative approach. We applied content analysis to scrutinize the gathered data, addressing the central question: 'Which strategies and techniques within organizational culture are essential for efficiently managing construction teams?' Our primary objectives were to clarify the intricate relationship between organizational culture and team management and outline key strategies crucial for effective team management. Consequently, the research revealed seven fundamental factors pivotal in facilitating effective team management, each accompanied by corresponding techniques. These factors encompass team formation and composition strategy, effective communication with the project team, employee development, team members' support, empowerment and autonomy, cultivation of a collaborative culture of trust and respect, and recognition and rewards policy. This study offers crucial insights into the correlation between organizational culture and successful construction team management, identifying vital strategies and techniques to enhance productivity, cohesion, and efficiency within construction teams

Keywords: Construction Industry; Content Analysis; Effective Team Management; Organizational Culture; Strategies and Techniques; Team Formation.

1. Introduction

Team management is a critical managerial approach that places a central emphasis on fostering the development and functioning of teams within organizations. This approach involves the application of principles and strategies aimed at enhancing employee productivity and facilitating self-organization and self-management through collaborative activities, mutual oversight, assistance, and interchangeability among team members. At its core, team management seeks to harness both individual and collective potentials within a team, foster a shared understanding of values and goals that guide the behavior of each team member, and promote a sense of collective responsibility for the team's performance outcomes (Kobushko et al., 2020). Therefore, "the success of business organizations and institutions is intrinsically linked to their ability to create cooperative work environments and effectively manage teamwork" (Zubonov et al., 2017, p.68). As such, comprehending the elements that contribute to effective teamwork is of paramount importance for project leaders looking to implement successful team management techniques and actions.

While the existing literature offers insights into the management of construction project teams from various angles, such as project manager competency, team success, and leadership, it is noteworthy that many scholars, including Zhang et al. (2022), Hrvatin et al. (2022), Amoah (2021), Soni (2020), Akhavan et al. (2014), and Dainty et al. (2005), have predominantly explored these aspects rather than focusing on the concept of team management itself. This suggests a

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gap in the research where team management as a distinct area of study remains underrepresented in the construction industry.

Furthermore, previous studies examining organizational culture have primarily concentrated on its influence on corporate performance (Pathiranage et al., 2020), employee satisfaction and performance (Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020) and (Kucharska et al., 2019), knowledge management success (Fong & Kwok, 2009), project management methodology (Piwowar-Sulej, 2021), sustainable development of enterprises (Mingaleva et al., 2022), job performance (Putra et al., 2020) and more (Mohsen et al., 2020). However, there appears to be a significant research gap in the exploration of how organizational culture influences team management.

Hence, it becomes apparent that there is an unaddressed need to investigate the impact of organizational culture on team management. Understanding this relationship is critical for enhancing the effectiveness of team management practices, as it may provide valuable insights into how organizational culture can be leveraged to optimize team performance and outcomes. This study seeks to fill this research gap by investigating the interplay between organizational culture and team management, shedding light on the mechanisms through which organizational culture can be harnessed to achieve more effective and efficient team management within construction projects. As Olynick and Li (2020) asserted, "It is imperative that organizational culture be better understood. Knowledge gained from research focused on this problem is crucial for addressing an evident paucity in knowledge, as well as providing recommendations that can be used by organizational leaders for quality improvement and employee relations." (p.14)

Study Objectives and Aims

The study, "Investigating the Influence of Organizational Culture on Team Management: Exploring Effective Factors and Techniques," was guided by two primary objectives aimed at enhancing the understanding of this relationship:

1.1. Investigation of Organizational Culture and Team Management

The first focus of this research was to undertake a thorough exploration of organizational culture and team management. This involved a detailed examination of past research concerning organizational culture and its impact on team management. Our primary goal was to discern and clarify the crucial factors that contributed to achieving successful team management, drawing from insights and findings in existing studies.

1.2. Identifying Essential Strategies and Techniques of Organizational Culture for Team Management

An additional key goal of this study was to identify and record the critical strategies and actions related to an organizational culture that facilitated the successful management of construction teams. This involved a comprehensive analysis of best practices from the viewpoints of both construction team members and project managers, with the aim of pinpointing methods and approaches that consistently led to positive results. Through this endeavor, the intention was to develop a comprehensive framework that outlined the essential factors and techniques organizations could employ to enhance their team management processes.

To summarize, this research study delved into the complexities of managing construction teams and uncovered the foundational strategies and methods necessary for cultivating an effective organizational culture that bolstered team management. The overarching aspiration was to provide the construction industry with valuable insights, ultimately striving to enhance industry practices and improve project outcomes through the accomplishment of these goals.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Organizational Culture and Team Management

The project team operates within a cultural incubator embedded within the organization rather than in an isolated setting. "Organizational culture includes an organization's expectations, experiences, philosophy, and values that hold it together and is expressed in its self-image, inner workings, interactions with the outside world, and future expectations" (Fokina & Krupnov, 2020, p. 1). Therefore, "effective organizational culture involves shared values and a common purpose to develop a sense of teamwork" (Pathiranage et al., 2020, p. 528). Thus, "the importance of organizational culture is increasing in the context of globalization. New approaches to the organization of work, especially in the management of innovative activities, have a strong impact on the mentality of employees, changing their attitudes to the values of working in a team and affecting their perceptions and assessments of innovations' importance for the enterprise" (Mingaleva et al., 2022, p. 2). Therefore, organizational culture aspects that the organization shares among the employees reflect its willingness toward teamwork and its success in team management.

The organization's work policy and its environment represent the organizational culture that has a great impact on the team's stability, success, and productivity. Piwowar-Sulej (2021) Argued, "Organizational culture – like the subconscious – affects the aspirations, attitudes, and behavior of employees" (p. 1272). Katane and Dube (2017) Articulated the influence of organizational culture and mentioned that "the organizational culture and factors such as good leadership, trust, communication, and team commitment played a bigger role in the success of the project teams" (p. 6). Mohsen et al (2020) Studied the impact of organizational culture on performance and argued that "elements of organizational culture influence the employee performance positively, particularly in achieving goals, coordinated team, customer orientation, and culture strength" (p.886).

In a study by Dolgov et al. (2006), the significance of organizational culture was underscored, as well as pinpointing the essential factors that influence the implementation and progression of team management within an organization. These factors include:

- The willingness of the organization's leadership to promote team development.
- The capacity of management team members and top executives to act as leaders within their respective functional teams.
- The level of ambition associated with the company's strategic and operational objectives, which should be well-known to all employees.
- The presence of effective feedback mechanisms between different levels of management.
- The establishment of a transparent system for both material and non-material incentives, aligning employee efforts with personal and collective effectiveness.
- The effectiveness of organizational philosophy as a management tool.
- The study highlighted the multifaceted nature of organizational culture and its pivotal role in shaping effective team management practices.

A study by Fong and Kwok (2009) explored the relationship between organizational culture and knowledge success within contracting firms, both at the project and organizational levels. The findings of the research unveiled that the Clan culture was predominant at both project and organizational levels. This implies that the culture within contracting firms heavily relies on values such as open and honest communication, respect for individuals, trust, and fostering strong interpersonal relationships. Interestingly, their study also highlighted a somewhat unexpected observation regarding respect for individuals, a value typically associated with Clan culture. Respect ranked relatively low, taking the 8th position out of 11 values for both project and organizational settings. This lower ranking doesn't imply that respect is unimportant; rather, it suggests that even in close-knit projects or organizational environments, varying personal values, beliefs, or distinct personal and organizational objectives might influence the level of respect among individuals. The authors pointed out that senior management should be cognizant of this phenomenon, as the ability to effectively manage people becomes challenging when there is a lack of respect among employees. They argued that in the construction industry, which is not only project-based but also inherently people-oriented, understanding and addressing these cultural dynamics is crucial for successful management and collaboration.

Moreover, Fitria (2018) Emphasized the profound influence of organizational culture on employee behavior. The author contended that "culture becomes deeply ingrained within an organization, often spreading unconsciously among its members. Organizational culture, in this sense, acts as a social glue, fostering a sense of belonging and an integral part of the organizational journey" (p. 83). Further, Fitria argued that "employees are inherently motivated to internalize the cultural values and norms of their organization, primarily because it fulfills their need for social identity and a sense of making sense of their work environment" (p.84). In essence, Fitria's perspective underscores the importance of organizational culture as a foundational element that not only shapes employee behavior but also serves as a catalyst for creating a shared sense of purpose and understanding within the workplace.

In a study by Paais and Pattiruhu (2020), the authors highlighted the connection between employee job satisfaction and the alignment of work motivation, leadership, and the organizational culture within a company. They stressed that "these elements should be well-integrated and accepted by all employees. Organizations bear the responsibility of providing appropriate resources, establishing a safe work environment, and offering support to teams as and when needed" (p.577). These influences were supported by Putra et al (2020) that "organizations must provide adequate work environment such as the physical environment (comfortable office layout, clean environment, good air system, color, adequate lighting), as well as the non-physical environment (relationship with superiors, relationships between colleagues, relationship with the subordinate" (p. 2).

In a separate research effort conducted by Rahman et al. (2020), the study delved into the factors that influence the success of highway projects in Malaysia. The researchers argued that "effective top-level management plays a pivotal

role in contributing to project success. This is achieved by ensuring the availability of sufficient funds upfront, thereby providing crucial financial support. Moreover, top management actively engages with project teams through site visits, offering valuable feedback and motivation to team members, which, in turn, extends essential emotional support” (p 6).

Furthermore, a study examining the influence of organizational culture and capabilities on fostering employee commitment to ethical conduct, as conducted by Lee (2020), unveiled that a “well-functioning organizational culture serves as a potent motivator for employees. This motivation stems from the encouragement of better-quality performance, achieved through collaboration and the practice of ethical work behavior. In essence, the study underscores the critical role of organizational culture in fostering ethical conduct and enhanced performance among employees” (p.47).

The importance of organizational culture transcends the understanding of operational constraints for individuals and teams; it also plays a role in the selection criteria and process for individuals. As Bell and Brown (2015) asserted in their study, "The first step in forming cohesive teams is to develop a comprehensive understanding of the organizational context in which these teams will operate" (p.193). Therefore, as Payne and Harpe (2020) argued, "the team member selection process should prioritize team building and collaboration" (p. 3). This implies that “assembling the right combination of team members, establishing norms, and defining clear tasks are essential to fostering positive team spirit and dynamics,” as suggested (Al-Malki & Juan, 2018, p. 53).

To conclude, the impact of organizational culture on team management spans various critical dimensions, affecting team operations, employee behavior, job satisfaction, and ethical conduct. Understanding and nurturing a positive organizational culture is pivotal for successful team management, employee satisfaction, and achieving organizational goals.

3. Summary of the Influence of Organizational Culture Factors on Team Management

The influence of organizational culture on project team management is a multifaceted and critical aspect that significantly impacts various dimensions of team operations. The literature review reveals several key factors related to organizational culture and its impact on project team management, illustrated in Table 1 and summarized below:

- **Shared Values and Common Purpose:** Effective organizational culture involves shared values and a common purpose, fostering a sense of teamwork and collaboration among team members.
- **Innovation:** Organizational culture affects attitudes toward working in a team and their perception of the importance of innovation for the enterprise.
- **Team Commitment:** Organizational culture, along with factors like good leadership, trust, communication, and team commitment, significantly contributes to the success of the project team.
- **Motivation System:** Elements of organizational culture positively influence employee performance, particularly in achieving goals, coordinated teamwork, customer orientation, and cultural strength.
- **Ethical Work Behaviors:** Organizational culture can foster ethical work behavior among employees, leading to improved performance and collaboration.
- **Team Support and Development:** A positive organizational culture is essential in establishing a nurturing work environment, facilitating team development, and enhancing employee job satisfaction.
- **Work Environment:** The organization's work policy and environment significantly affect the team's stability, success, and productivity.
- **Selection Criteria and Process:** Organizational culture influences the selection criteria and process for team members, emphasizing the importance of team building and collaboration.
- **Knowledge of Strategic Goals:** Employees' knowledge of the organization's strategic and operational objectives is essential for effective team management.

Table 1 Organizational Culture Factors From Literature

Organizational Culture Factors	Clarification
Shared Values and Common Purpose	The alignment of values and a unified purpose.
Innovation	Encouraging and fostering a culture of innovation.
Team Commitment	The dedication and loyalty of team members.

Motivation System	The mechanisms that drive and maintain motivation within teams.
Ethical Work Behaviours	Adherence to ethical principles and conduct in the workplace.
Team Support	Providing essential support to the team's efforts.
Teams Development	The continuous improvement and growth of teams.
Work Environment	The physical and social setting in which teams operate.
Selection Criteria & Process	The standards and procedures for selecting team members.
Knowledge of Strategic Goals	Awareness of the company's strategic and operational objectives.

3.1. Study Problem and Questions

While the theory of team interaction processes has seen gradual improvement, it is evident that certain aspects of team interaction require continued attention (Wang, 2018). Recognizing the evolving nature of engineering challenges, it is acknowledged that engineers must possess not only scientific expertise but also non-scientific skills, such as recognizing limitations, acquiring new knowledge, and fostering strong teamwork and communication abilities (Ismail et al., 2019). Consequently, there exists an unmet need to explore the influence of organizational culture on team management, signifying a gap in the existing literature on construction projects

This study aims to fill this void by conducting a comprehensive investigation into the impact of organizational culture on construction team management, as perceived by both managers and members of construction project teams. The inquiry is driven by the recognition that understanding these dynamics is crucial for addressing challenges effectively in the construction industry. Therefore, the ensuing question is posed in pursuit of these research objectives:

- *Which strategies and techniques of organizational culture are essential for effectively managing construction teams?*

4. Research Methodology

This exploratory research consisted of two crucial steps in the research design, as depicted in **Figure 1**. The research framework utilized the qualitative method in data collection and analysis.

Figure 1 Research Design

In the first step, the research began by reviewing factors and elements contributing to the effectiveness of a team based on existing literature and theories. These influential factors were identified to serve as a foundation for the subsequent step. It's worth noting that these factors were not specific to construction teams but were derived from broader team-related studies.

In the second step, questionnaires were developed to explore practical techniques and factors of organizational culture necessary for managing construction project teams. Data were collected from expert project managers and team members who had led successful projects in the past. The objective was to address the research question and discern the influential factors and techniques related to the organizational culture that contribute to the effective management of construction teams.

For step two, qualitative data was collected through in-depth interviews with nine expert project managers and project team members. Interviews were conducted individually in a face-to-face, and semi-structured format to provide the researcher with control and the ability to delve deeply into participants' experiences. The questions posed were clear and straightforward, drawing from insights identified in the literature, Appendix 1. This approach aimed to avoid leading or provocative questions. The interviews were recorded and securely stored to ensure data preservation.

Data analysis involved qualitative analysis using content analysis. Thematic analysis was applied, which included stages such as initial coding, construction of broader themes, and the development of overarching concepts.

In summary, this research used a qualitative method approach for data collection and analysis to comprehensively explore the factors and techniques that influence effective construction team management.

5. Data Collection and Analysis

5.1. In-depth Interview

A sequence of comprehensive, face-to-face interviews took place separately with nine team members from diverse backgrounds and roles within their organization. Each interview was structured to allow participants to share their personal experiences and perspectives regarding organizational cultural influence on team management. The objective was to gain valuable insights into how various organizational cultural factors and techniques influence team management. The content analysis technique was employed to extract recurring themes and patterns from the interviewees' responses.

5.2. Interviewees Overview

Table 2 is a comprehensive source of information pertaining to the individuals who took part in the study. It presents a detailed overview of the participants, encompassing essential data regarding their professional background, specifically focusing on their years of experience within the realm of construction projects, the type of organizations they are affiliated with, and the specific roles they undertake within these organizations.

Table 2 Interviewees' Professional Information

Interviewee	Organization Type	Position	Years of Experience
Interviewee 1	Consultant	Cost control and contract engineer	28
Interviewee 2	Consultant	Project Manager	25
Interviewee 3	Consultant	Contracts Manager	27
Interviewee 4	Client	Project Manager	9
Interviewee 5	Consultant	Senior Resident Engineer	46
Interviewee 6	Consultant	Resident Engineer	29
Interviewee 7	Contractor	Senior Civil Engineer	15
Interviewee 8	Consultant	Resident Engineer	30
Interviewee 9	Client	Team Leader	25

5.3. Interview Results

Appendix 2 offers a brief overview outlining the different themes and sub-themes derived from the insights shared by seasoned construction project practitioners. The appendix includes information obtained from experienced professionals, shedding light on the central role played by organizational culture in influencing the dynamics, functionality, and success of construction project teams.

5.4. Interview Analysis

In the research interviews, we found many important and recurring themes and valuable ideas. **Table 3**, provided a concise yet comprehensive presentation of the diverse themes encapsulating the fundamental ideas articulated within the interview responses. Each of these overarching themes is intricately complemented by a set of sub-themes that delve into specific facets, thereby offering a nuanced perspective on the overarching concept of the influence of organizational culture on team management in construction projects.

Among the prominent findings, it was apparent that participants widely acknowledged the organization's profound emphasis on key areas such as communication, diversity, and inclusion. These cultural factors significantly influenced team dynamics and contributed to a sense of cohesion among team members. The commitment to fostering an inclusive environment was perceived as a cornerstone of effective team management.

Furthermore, the importance of selecting team members with the right skills emerged as a unanimous consensus among the interviewees. This strategic approach to team composition was seen as a pivotal driver for enabling effective problem-solving and decision-making within the construction teams. It was evident that the organization's focus on assembling teams with the appropriate skill sets positively impacted overall team performance.

A recurring theme that resonated with many participants was the value placed on regular problem-solving meetings. These meetings were regarded as an indispensable tool for enhancing team collaboration. By providing a platform for addressing challenges and brainstorming solutions, such meetings played a crucial role in maintaining a collaborative and productive team environment.

In addition, the interviews underscored the significance of clear career development strategies within the organization. The availability of workshops, seminars, and various learning opportunities was considered an invaluable asset for team members seeking to enhance their skills and advance their careers. The organization's commitment to facilitating continuous learning and growth was widely appreciated by the interviewees.

Similarly, the availability of professional and management training programs was perceived positively by the participants. These programs were seen as instrumental in equipping team members with the necessary skills and knowledge to excel in their roles. The proactive approach to providing opportunities for skill development and career advancement was acknowledged as a testament to the organization's commitment to its employees.

Interviewees highly appreciated the emphasis on delegation as a technique for enhancing team skills. Delegation not only encourages skill development but also fosters trust and responsibility among team members. It is seen as a catalyst for promoting autonomy within the team. Empowering teams to make their decisions and exercise autonomy was seen as a cornerstone of effective team management. It promotes a sense of ownership, accountability, and motivation among team members, serving as a driving force for innovation and problem-solving within the team.

Interviewees acknowledged the importance of clear performance evaluation criteria. It enables team members to understand how their contributions are assessed and aligned with organizational objectives. Clarity in evaluation criteria promotes fairness and transparency, essential for team morale and motivation.

Interviewees underscored the importance of an organizational culture that prioritizes respect, trust, and collaboration. These cultural values form the foundation for effective team management and enable team members to work cohesively toward common goals. Ensuring that team members are aware of the organization's culture, vision, mission, and values was considered essential. This awareness reinforces alignment with the organization's goals and helps create a shared sense of purpose among team members.

Encouraging team members to express and share their ideas was acknowledged as a valuable technique for promoting collaboration and innovation. It creates an inclusive environment where diverse perspectives are considered, leading to more effective decision-making.

Recognizing and rewarding high-performance achievements were considered motivating and reinforcing positive behavior. Such recognition encourages team members to strive for excellence and fosters a sense of accomplishment. Providing competitive and fair wages for team members was seen as an integral part of a recognition and rewards policy. Competitive compensation acknowledges the value of team members' contributions and enhances their job satisfaction.

In conclusion, the findings from these interviews underscore the significance of the examined organizational cultural factors and techniques influencing effective team management. Each factor and technique played a crucial role in creating a collaborative, inclusive, and empowered team environment that fosters trust, respect, and recognition. The research interviews not only revealed these key themes but also emphasized the organization's dedication to fostering a culture that values effective communication, skillful team composition, collaborative problem-solving, career development, and ongoing learning. These cultural factors collectively contributed to the successful management of construction teams and the achievement of organizational goals.

Table 3 Organizational Culture Factors and Techniques for Construction Team Management

Organizational Culture Factors	Organizational Culture Techniques
Team Formation and Composition Strategy	Communicate organizational values with the team
	Implementing policies and practices that promote diversity, equity, and inclusion
	Fill the team with the right people that having problem-solving, decision-making, and interpersonal skills
	Utilizing enough members of the team
	Promote responsibility and accountability
	Encourage Communication between top management and

Effective Communication with the project Team	the project team
	Provide tools and resources to facilitate communication
	Arranging regular meetings to solve problems that may face the team
	Communicate project status with the team
	Allow team members to speak up about any issue in the project openly
Employee Development	Clear strategies and policies for employees' career path development
	Organizing regular workshops, seminars, and related courses
	Provide the team with learning opportunities
	Providing professional and management training for the team members
Team members Support	Provide the necessary requirements such as cars, computers, and software programs, standards, specifications, and legal advice
	Establish a secure and healthy environment for the team
	Adopting convenient work timing for the team
	Giving employees the space they need
	Correcting and providing feedback
	Support team leader and employees in building team cohesion
	Motivating the team to achieve goals
	Provide coaching and mentorship to team members, either through in-house programs or by partnering with external coaches and mentors
	Treat the team fairly and provide support when needed
Empowerment and Autonomy	Emphasizing delegation to enhance team skills
	Avoid micromanagement
	Availability of a clear action plan and its updates
	Empower teams to make their own decisions and give them autonomy
	Clearly define roles, responsibilities, and expectations for every team member
	Provide clear performance evaluation criteria
	Emphasize flexibility such as remote work options, flexible hours , and job sharing
	Providing project management software can greatly help organize the work of the team members
	Keep the team informed about organization's vision and values
	Empower team members to lead
Encouraging a Culture of Collaboration, Trust, and Respect	Allowing team members to express and share ideas
	Encourage a culture of respect, trust, and collaboration
	Sharing regular sports, picnics, and entertainment activities with the team
	Organizational management should meet their teams and celebrate lunch with them to encourage collaboration between team members
	Provide awareness for the team about the company culture,

	vision, mission, and values
	Build trust among the team members and make it an essential value
	Encourage feedback
Recognition and Rewards Policy	Awarding and rewarding high-performance achievements
	Offering reasonable wages for team members
	Providing relevant personal services for the team members

6. Discussion

The primary objective of this study is to identify and document critical strategies and actions related to organizational culture that contribute to the successful management of teams. The research results offer valuable insights into the central role played by organizational culture in shaping the dynamics, functionality, and success of construction project teams. Collectively, these findings underscore the vital role of organizational culture and specific techniques in influencing effective team management within the construction industry, as illustrated in Table 3.

Pham et al (2021) Explore the influence of organizational culture dimensions, including work environment, salary, rewards, empowerment, management style, and corporate values, on employees' satisfaction and organizational commitment. The authors support the research findings related to team member support, emphasizing the importance of managers understanding employees' needs and abilities to create a dynamic environment through their actions and a more participatory attitude. They further support organizational cultural factors influencing team management, including recognition and rewards policy, empowerment and autonomy, and employee development. Mingaleva et al (2022) recommend that organizations help “employees master the entire system of organizational values through internal recognition and promotion of those serving as role models” (p. 2). (Putra, et al (2020) recommend that “organizations continue shaping their culture through compensation programs derived from organizational and leadership policies, emphasizing the role of work environment and organizational culture” (p.11).

Bell and Brown (2015) advocate for team formation and composition strategies, stating that “teams are best positioned for success when certain enabling conditions are in place, such as the right mix of individuals. They emphasize the importance of developing a general understanding of the organizational context within which teams will operate” (pp. 181-193). Pham and Dinh (2020) emphasize the significance of fostering a culture of collaboration, trust, respect, and effective communication, stating that an open culture requires companies to create a friendly environment for sharing, conversation, and collaboration. Katane and Dube (2017) find that organizational culture has a definite influence on the success of virtual project teams, with team communication and orientation identified as crucial factors. Fitria, (2018) asserts the direct positive effect of organizational culture and trust on employee performance, suggesting that focusing on these variables can enhance overall employee performance.

Mingaleva et al. (2022) assert the importance of team formation and composition strategy, stating that organizations should identify employees whose personality traits and belief systems align with the desired organizational culture, referring to them as "cultural donors".

Organizations that prioritize these aspects, as outlined in Table 3, can expect a more productive, collaborative, and motivated workforce, ultimately leading to project success. Therefore, organizations should cultivate and communicate a culture that values respect, trust, and collaboration. This culture serves as the foundation for cohesive teamwork, alignment with organizational goals, and shared purpose among team members. Organizations must adopt a deliberate approach to assemble teams with the appropriate skill sets. This strategy enhances overall team performance, facilitating better problem-solving and decision-making for achieving project goals and deadlines. Organizations should actively provide opportunities for skill development and career advancement, as well as encourage delegation to benefit both individual team members and the organization. This commitment to continuous learning and growth ensures a skilled and motivated workforce as well as fostering responsibility among team members.

Organizations should establish transparent evaluation processes, clarifying performance expectations and aligning them with team success. This is vital for maintaining team morale and motivation. Organizations should implement recognition and reward policies to encourage team members to excel, fostering a sense of accomplishment. Providing competitive and fair wages is integral to acknowledging the value of team members' contributions and enhancing job satisfaction.

6.1. Research Limitations and Recommendations

However, it is essential to acknowledge and carefully consider several limitations inherent in this study. Firstly, the research employed a qualitative approach for data collection and analysis, with only nine team members contributing. This limited sample size can lead to low internal validity. To address this limitation, future studies are encouraged to adopt larger sample sizes and employ multifaceted approaches, such as the triangulation concept, for data collection and analysis. This methodological enhancement can contribute to bolstering the validity and reliability of the research findings.

While the study included participants from both private and public sectors, it is noteworthy that these sectors exhibit distinct cultural aspects and variations in performance measurements, as highlighted by (AL-Swidi et al., 2021). Recognizing this, future research endeavors might overcome this limitation by focusing on each sector separately. By doing so, a more nuanced understanding of the influence of organizational culture on team management within each sector could be obtained, minimizing potential confounding factors arising from sectoral differences.

Another limitation pertains to the static nature of the acquired data. The evaluation of existing organizational culture concentrated on appraisals of its impact on team management at a specific moment. Regrettably, the study did not delve into the dynamic shifts occurring in organizational culture over time. Consequently, there is a lack of examination regarding how these changes might influence key indicators related to factors and methods essential for efficiently managing construction teams. To address this, future research should incorporate a longitudinal perspective to capture the evolving nature of organizational culture and its consequential effects on construction team management practices. This would offer a more comprehensive and dynamic comprehension of the correlation between organizational culture and effective team management within the construction industry.

Considering the findings of this research, several recommendations for future studies and areas of exploration can be identified. Future studies could delve deeper into strategies and best practices for strategic team composition. Examining how organizations identify and assemble teams with the right skill sets and the impact of these strategies on construction project outcomes could be a fruitful area of investigation. Further research can examine the practices and techniques of delegation within construction teams. Understanding how delegation is used to empower team members, promote innovation, and enhance problem-solving can inform effective team management strategies. Future studies could consider the long-term impact of these practices and cultural factors on project success and organizational performance. Moreover, Further investigations are recommended to explore the design and effectiveness of recognition and reward policies within the construction industry. Analyzing how different recognition strategies influence team members' motivation, performance, and job satisfaction. Future studies can focus on the development and implementation of clear performance evaluation criteria in construction organizations. Investigating how transparent evaluation processes impact team morale and motivation, and how they contribute to project success. Future research can adopt specific cultural typologies such as clan, adhocracy, hierarchy, and market culture to investigate the influence of each culture on the construction team and explore the factors and techniques that contribute to effective construction team management.

7. Conclusion

This research emphasizes the pivotal role of organizational culture and management practices in shaping the performance of construction project teams. Interviews with experienced professionals identified key factors critical for team cohesion and project success.

Notably, the study underscores the importance of fostering a culture of communication, diversity, and inclusion in construction organizations, enhancing team dynamics, and productivity. Strategic team composition emerged as a significant driver of overall team performance, emphasizing the importance of selecting skilled team members for effective problem-solving and meeting project goals. Learning opportunities within the organization were acknowledged for skill development, benefiting individual team members and the organization's success. Delegation was highlighted for promoting trust, autonomy, and innovation. Transparent performance evaluation criteria fostered fairness and motivation, aligning contributions with organizational objectives.

In general, these findings underscore the crucial significance of these factors and techniques in managing construction teams, potentially improving project outcomes and overall organizational success.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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Appendix 1

Appendix 1

|

Inquiries Regarding Organizational Culture

- 1- What does your organization do to support team management?

- 2- Do you think your organization can do things differently to support team management?
And what is that?

- 3- Based on your experience, could you highlight the most crucial factors or elements that organizations should focus on to assist you in effectively managing your team??

- 4- What actions should organizations or top management avoid to prevent issues that might impact team performance, synergy, motivation, and minimize conflicts or struggles within teams?

- 5- Is there anything else you'd like to suggest regarding how organizations can assist and bolster project managers in effectively overseeing construction teams?"

Appendix 2

Summary of Themes and Sub-Themes Identified from Organizational Culture Questions

Theme of Organizational Culture	Sub-Themes Identified from Organizational Culture Questions								
	Interviewee 1	Interviewee 2	Interviewee 3	Interviewee 4	Interviewee 5	Interviewee 6	Interviewee 7	Interviewee 8	Interviewee 9
Effective Communication	1- Communicate openly and transparently	1- Strong communication between the project team 2- Communication with top management 3- Regular reporting on project status	-	-	1- Arranging regular meetings to solve problems the team may face	1- Encourage clear and frequent communication 2- Maintain good communication between team members and leadership	-	1- Encourage communication 2- Provide tools and resources to facilitate communication	1- Include the project teams in all official emails and communications 2- Let team members speak up about any issue in the project openly
Employee Training and Development	-	-	1- Provide training for the staff 2- Clear strategies and policies for employees' career path development	1- Providing training for the team 2- Emphasizing delegation to enhance team skills	1- Enhancing the qualification /experience of team members 2- Organizing regular workshops, seminars & related courses	1- Provide the team with learning opportunities	-	1- Provide training and development opportunities	1- Provide training for the team
Planning and Task Distribution	1- Delegate tasks based on strengths	1- Introducing a	-	-	-	1- Clearly define roles and	1- Focus on the working plan	1- Provide clear goals and	Provide clear performance

	<p>2- Promote efficiency and avoid micromanagement</p> <p>3- Using good project management software can greatly help organize the work</p>	<p>general action plan</p> <p>2- Distributing tasks</p> <p>3- Availability of a clear action plan and its updates</p> <p>4- Follow-up on the team's progress</p> <p>5- Monitoring the team's performance</p> <p>6- Controlling the team's activities</p> <p>6- Regular reporting on project status</p>				<p>responsibilities for every team member</p> <p>2- Keep the team informed</p>	<p>2- Completing activities during the working plan</p> <p>3- Following up with the project manager</p>	<p>expectations</p> <p>2-Emphasize flexibility such as remote work options, flexible hours, and job sharing</p>	<p>evaluation criteria</p>
Team members Support	-	<p>1- Supporting team members</p> <p>2- Correcting and providing feedback</p>	<p>1-Top management should arrange essential tools such as cars and</p>	<p>1- Being close to the projects team</p> <p>2- Providing required tools and software</p>	-	<p>1- Giving employees space they need</p>	-	<p>1-Provide coaching and mentorship to team members, either through in-</p>	<p>1- Treat the team fairly and provide support when needed</p>

			computers on time 1- Provide legal advice 2- Provide updated rules, standards, and specifications	3- Motivating the team to achieve goals				house programs or by partnering with external coaches and mentors	
Empowerment and Autonomy	-	-	-	-	-	1- Give teams autonomy in decision-making 2- Empower teams to make their own decisions	-	1- Encourage autonomy by delegating decision-making responsibilities to the team 2- Empower team members to lead projects	1- Delegation of top management's authorities to team leader 2- Delegation of project manager's authorities to the project team 2- Delegate responsibilities appropriately
Effective Team Meetings	-	-	-	-	-	1- Manage team meetings wisely	-	-	1- Provide regular official & unofficial meetings with your

									team, such as every week to have lunch in the office together
Collaboration	1- Allowing them to share ideas 2- Support employees in building team cohesion 3- Create a culture of ideas and innovation 4- Make trust an essential value	-	-	-	-	-	-	1- Foster a culture of collaboration 2- Encourage feedback	-
Health, Safety, and Work Environment	-	-	-	-	1- Providing a safe & healthy environment for the team 2- Adopting convenient work timing for the team	-	-	1- Foster a culture of safety	
Team Formation and Composition	1- Establish a clear				1- Utilizing enough	1- Build diverse and		1- Foster diversity and	

	organizational purpose 2- Promote ownership and accountability 3- Reward teams for taking risks				members of the team	inclusive teams 2- Filling the team with the right people having communication, problem-solving, decision-making, and interpersonal skills		inclusion by implementing policies and practices that support diversity, equity, and inclusion	
Recognition and Rewards	-	1- Availability of benefits for team members 2- Awarding high-performance members	-	-	1- Offering reasonable wages for team members 2- Providing relevant personal services for the team 3- Giving rewards and encouragement to the team 4- Sharing regular sports, picnics &		1- Foster a culture of respect, trust, and collaboration 2- Encourage feedback		

					entertainment activities with the team				
Respect and Trust						1- Build trust within the team			Trust the team